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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
WP5	D5.2	D27	Formalize the ENLIGHT Innovation Network	NUIG

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	D26

Description (short)
This report on the formalization of the ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network (ERIN) will list the organisations identified under the Health & Well-Being Flagship as the first iteration of the ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network (ERIN). These organisations were identified as part of the D26 mapping of academy-industry partnerships, and will be invited to partake in the ENLIGHT RISE AIMday®. This report outlines the network attributes and its governance structure and terms of reference for the Innovation Network. Based on lessons learned through this approach, additional ERIN's will be established for other ENLIGHT Flagships.

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Introduction

ENLIGHT is a European network formed by nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (University of the Basque Country in Spain, University of Bordeaux in France, Comenius University Bratislava in Slovakia, University of Galway in Ireland, Ghent University in Belgium, University of Göttingen in Germany, University of Groningen in the Netherlands, University of Tartu in Estonia, Uppsala University in Sweden).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance.

The ENLIGHT alliance gathers a strong knowledge community composed of highly competitive, entrepreneurial universities, increasingly networked with businesses and society. Linked to these instruments, the aim of ENLIGHT RISE WP5 is to develop a map of academy-industry partnerships related to the five ENLIGHT flagship challenges, to explore strengths and weaknesses and to define what an ENLIGHT virtual European Innovation District might look like with an overall goal of boosting European entrepreneurial and innovation capacity.

This report represents D27 (D5.2), the specific activities of which are as follows:

- (i) Formally invite industry partners identified under D26 to become members of the ERIN.
- (ii) Establish the members, governance, agenda of the ERIN

Method

A WP2 report produced a list of over 8,000 industry partners across the alliance (see deliverable D26). Using this list as a basis for discussion during the workshop held in Bratislava, the WP5 team identified key strategic industry partners under the flagship heading of Health and Well-Being that will be invited to join the ERIN. As part of this communication, these industry partners will also be invited to attend an event in Galway in May 2023. This will consist of an Academic Industry Meeting day

(AIMday®) using the Uppsala model and will be held in partnership with the ENLIGHT European Dialogue event. The theme of the European Dialogue is 'Digital Innovation in Health & Wellbeing' and as well as an AIMday® the event will include keynote speakers from academics working in the area and the Director responsible for Health Systems, Medical Products & Innovation from DG SANTE of the European Commission.

The invitation, will be issued commencing week 13th February 2023, sets-out the value of joining the ENLIGHT network and the expectation of participation, is shown below:

Letter of Invitation to join the ENLIGHT Innovation District Network

Dear [name],

I am writing on behalf the ENLIGHT Alliance to invite you to join the ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network (ERIN) for Health and Well-being. ENLIGHT is a European university alliance of nine research-intensive universities from around Europe (Belgium, Germany, France, The Netherlands, Spain, Estonia, Slovakia, Sweden & Ireland). More information may be found on the [ENLIGHT](#) website.

The role of the ERIN is to leverage our economic, network and physical assets across the ENLIGHT regions to increase our innovative capacity and capability while also contributing to regional economic development. We will focus on flagship areas:

- Health & Well-being
- Digital revolution and Impact of digitization
- Climate change
- Energy & Circular economy
- Equity

By joining this alliance, you will have a unique opportunity to identify valuable new research and innovation opportunities and partnerships with domain experts from within the alliance. We anticipate your involvement will include:

- Contribute to European Dialogue Days to build knowledge and networks
- Participate in AIMday® to identify new collaborative research opportunities across the ENLIGHT network
- Other engagements identified by ERIN partners

To kick-off this ERIN, we will host an event in Galway on 24-25 May 2023. This ENLIGHT European Dialogue will bring together ENLIGHT academics, students, industry partners, regional agencies and project staff from each of the nine ENLIGHT partners to discuss the challenges facing Europe under the theme, '*Digital Innovation in Health & Wellbeing*'. We would greatly appreciate your RSVP to indicate your interest in joining ERIN and participation at the Galway conference by 17 March 2023.

If you have any queries regarding this matter, please contact [name] or [name] on [telephone number/email].

ENLIGHT European Dialogue/AIMday®

The event is arranged to link the ENLIGHT Erasmus European Dialogue and the ENLIGHT RISE ERIN AIMday® to jointly define R&I priorities in relation to one of the flagship challenges. Based on the success and lessons learned from this initialisation, we will expand to other flagship challenges to create a robust and representative ERIN. The agenda, outlined below, is designed to take advantage of the European Dialogue and AIMday® concepts to ensure we will have an engaged, representative programme that will produce meaningful outcomes and partnerships.

ENLIGHT University Network – European Dialogue 2023

Digital Innovation in Health & Well-being

Hosted by University of Galway, co-hosted by Uppsala University, Sweden

The ENLIGHT European Dialogue brings together universities and external stakeholders to discuss solutions for the societal challenges we face today in our European regions and globally. The dialogue is a networking event where ENLIGHT universities engage with external stakeholders and each other, sharing best practices, and fostering future research and education collaborations. It also incorporates an AIMday® (Academic Industry Meeting Day) where inter-disciplinary researchers discuss challenges posed by industry partners and brainstorm innovative solutions, thus fostering learning, building new relationships and forging future collaborations.

University of Galway are delighted to host the second European Dialogue event on 23-25 May 2023 with the theme of '*Digital Innovation in Health and Well-being*'.

Galway is one of Europe's premier MedTech hubs and University of Galway is at the heart of this ecosystem. The European Dialogue 2023 will be a great opportunity for open and collaborative engagement and learning among all stakeholders - universities, industry and healthcare professionals. We look forward to welcoming you to Galway for what promises to be a fruitful conversation.

Tuesday 23 May 2023	
18:00-19:30	Welcome event: Drinks reception and finger food – Meet & Greet
Wednesday 24 May 2023	
08:30-09:00	<i>Registration & tea/coffee</i>
09:00-09:15	Welcome Address Intro – Professor Becky Whay , Vice President International, University of Galway President Ciarán Ó hÓgartaigh , University of Galway
09:15-10:00	Keynote: 'Overview of Galway's Digital Health Innovation Ecosystem' Professor Martin O Halloran , Biomedical Engineering, Director Bio innovate, Director Translational Medical Device Lab, Health Innovation Hub Ireland Co-lead, University of Galway
10:00-10:15	AIMday® Introduction Dr. Jenny Nordquist , Head at Innovation Partnership Office, Uppsala University, Sweden
10:15-10:45	<i>Tea/coffee</i>
10:45-11:45	AIMday® Session 1
12:00-13:00	AIMday® Session 2
13:00-14:15	Lunch
14:15-15:15	AIMday® Session 3
15:30-16:30	AIMday® Closing: roundtable of challenge owners to discuss next steps Dr. Jenny Nordquist , Head at Innovation Partnership Office, Uppsala University, Sweden Dr. Paul Dodd , Vice President Engagement, University of Galway
19:00-21:00	<i>Networking Reception & Dinner</i>
Thursday 25 May 2023	

09:00-09:20	<i>Tea/coffee</i>
09:20 –10:15	<p>Opening Address: Professor Martin O'Donnell, Executive Dean, College of Medicine, Nursing and Health Science</p> <p>Keynote: Dr. Andrzej Ryś, Director responsible for Health Systems, Medical Products and Innovation at DG SANTE, European Commission</p> <p>Q&A facilitated by Professor Martin O'Donnell</p>
10:15-11:00	<p>'Digital Health Innovation', Professor Derek O'Keeffe Consultant Endocrinologist at University Hospital Galway and Professor of Medical Device Technology, University of Galway</p> <p>'The role of Health Psychology in the digital transformation of healthcare' Professor Jane Walsh, Health Psychologist and Director of the Mobile Technology of Health (mHealth) Research Group.</p> <p>Q&A facilitated by Dr. Erik Olsson, Uppsala University, Sweden.</p>
11:00-11:30	<i>Tea/coffee</i>
11:30-11:45	<p>Workshop 'Creating ENLIGHT Thematic Networks'</p> <p>Igor Campillo, Director of Euskampus Foundation, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain</p>
11:45-13:15	Workshop 'Creating Connections': Thematic Workshops facilitated by ENLIGHT Partners
13:15-14:30	<i>Networking Lunch/ENLIGHT RISE Innovation District Governance</i>
14:00-15:00	Workshop 'Creating Connections' (continued): Thematic Workshops facilitated by ENLIGHT Partners
15:00-15:45	<p>Day 2 Wrap-up Roundtable - Creating ENLIGHT Networks, next steps</p> <p>Professor Becky Whay, Vice President International</p>
16:15-17:00	Cultural Outing (optional)
17:00 onwards	Free time to enjoy Galway City

An ENLIGHT RISE Innovation District Governance meeting will be held as part of the event in May to agree the proposed terms of reference, governance model, and agenda (see appendix) are appropriate for the Health Flagship Innovation District.

Appendix

ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network Governance Terms of Reference

Introduction

The ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network (ERIN) will provide ecosystems which are multi-stakeholder partnerships committed to working together to implement innovative solutions across the ENLIGHT Ecosystem.

ERIN will develop thematic ecosystems for each of the ENLIGHT Flagships (Health & Well-being, Digital revolution & Impact of digitization, Climate Change, Energy & Circular economy, Equity). These ecosystems comprised of ENLIGHT members, enterprise partners and regional partners will exchange ideas and collaborate on research and innovation opportunities.

Governance of ERIN will include a strategic board to coordinate the overall ecosystem while each Flagship Ecosystem will have a steering committee to ensure an engaged membership and to organise networking events.

Title:	ERIN Strategic Board
Purpose:	A Strategic Board shall be established to provide oversight and programme management to coordinate the full ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network.
Membership	<p>The Board shall comprise members, as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chairperson - appointment by the ENLIGHT European Office 1 representative from each of the ERIN Flagship Ecosystem Enterprise partners 1 representative from each of the ERIN lead institutions <p>Vice-Chairperson – The Chair may wish to appoint a vice-Chairperson to assist the Chairperson and, in their absence, chair board meetings.</p> <p>Nominees – Representatives may request attendance by a nominee</p> <p>Gender Balance – Minimum 40% male and 40% female members</p>
Term:	<p>Members will be appointed for a term of two years.</p> <p>Members may be appointed for a second term of two years.</p>
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop and maintain a future vision and strategic direction for ERIN, including strategies for inclusion and sustainability and linkage to the region's entrepreneurial ecosystems. 2. Provide oversight and advice on performance of individual components of the ecosystem, including generation of overall indicators and targets against which performance of the ecosystem and its components are measured. 3. Coordinate components of the ecosystem, including the creation and direction of the ERIN Flagship Ecosystems.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Promote and support ERIN Flagship Ecosystems and activities generally and specifically within the ENLIGHT institutions. 5. Consult, as appropriate with stakeholders external to ENLIGHT, such as European and regional economic development agencies and funders, to provide insight and perspective on trends and opportunities.
Reporting:	The Board shall report to << <i>to be decided at ERIN Governance meeting</i> >>. Agenda and minutes of board meeting will be made available to the European Office.
Meeting Frequency:	The Strategic Board will meet at least 2 times a year.
Meeting Quorum:	In addition to the Chair, or Vice-Chair, at least 40% members must be present.
Attendance:	Internal and external individuals or entities may be invited to attend Board meetings, steering group meetings, or part thereof, as required.

Title:	ERIN Flagship Ecosystem Steering Committee
Purpose:	<p>A Steering Committee shall be established for each Flagship to action three areas associated with ERIN Entrepreneurial Programmes and Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate and organise events and activities • Collaborate to address opportunities and challenges • Promote and celebrate successes
Membership	<p>The inclusive forum shall comprise members, as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chairperson – appointment by the ERIN Lead Institution <p>Membership of the Steering Committee will be broad with representation from enterprise, regional partners, researchers, and other stakeholders to ensure good communication and information exchange.</p> <p>To ensure efficient decision making the steering committee will be limited to 12 members rotating annually.</p> <p>Vice-Chairperson – The Chair may wish to appoint a Vice-Chairperson to assist the Chairperson and, in their absence, chair board meetings.</p> <p>Nominees – Representatives may request attendance by a nominee</p> <p>Gender Balance – Minimum 40% male and 40% female members</p>
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication and information exchange between components of the ecosystem. 2. Input to Strategic Board on ecosystem strategy. 3. Identify the need for new capabilities and funding gaps and work with the Strategic Board to progress those needs. 4. Coordinate regional programmes, training and events with a particular focus on AIMday®.

	<p>5. Identify and develop internal, regional, and international academic and industry partnerships.</p> <p>6. Promote entrepreneurial activities, impacts and successes.</p> <p>7. Devise and communicate cohesive messages to key stakeholders and funders.</p>
Reporting:	The Steering Committees will report periodically to the Strategic Board via the Chair or nominee.
Meeting Frequency:	<p>The Steering Committees will meet at least 2 times a year.</p> <p>The ENLIGHT European Office will provide administrative and logistical support.</p>
Attendance:	Internal and external individuals or entities may be invited by the Chair to attend meetings, or part thereof, as required.